

DEFENSE OF ATTORNEY`S SPEECH

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6497166>

Turaeva Shakhlo Alijon qizi

O`zbekiston Davlat Jahon Tillari Universiteti magistranti

Annotation: *standard in building a defensive speech, the Criminal Code, justify a lower level of responsibility, the exact circumstances, monitor the questions, atmosphere in the courtroom.*

Key words: *defense, defendant, defensive facts, verdict, unlawful, criminal element, human qualities, the gestures and actions, reconsider, duty.*

Annotatsiya: *himoya nutqini qurishdagi standart, Jinoyat kodeksi, yengil darajadagi javobgarlik, aniq holatlarni oqlaydi, savollarni kuzatib borish, sud zalidagi muhitni nazorat qiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *himoya, sudlanuvchi, himoya faktlari, hukm, qonunga xilof, jinoyiy tarkib, insoniy fazilatlar, imo-ishoralar va harakatlar, qayta ko'rib chiqish, burch.*

Аннотация: *стандарты построения оборонительной речи, Уголовный кодекс, обоснование низшей степени ответственности, точные обстоятельства, контрольные вопросы, атмосфера в зале суда.*

Ключевые слова: *защита, подсудимый, факты защиты, вердикт, неправомерность, преступный элемент, человеческие качества, жесты и действия, пересмотреть, обязанность.*

The defense attorney's defense will be sufficiently independent. According to this, the lawyer should clarify details and analyze all the circumstances of the case in terms of the defendant's defense, to provide all the information that is slaughtered in his favor will be The defender repeats his speech while working on the group to determine who says what so that it doesn't happen, the speeches of colleagues should coordinate with. However, the fact that there is no standard in building a defensive speech is a defense which means that there are no general requirements that the speech must meet it's not. Its content and structure cannot be free. They are at work the duties assigned to the lawyer and the specifics of the case in which he is acting depending on the features.

Based on the specific circumstances of the case, the lawyer:

- 1) the absence of criminal content in the actions of the defendant, the crime he is innocent because he was not present or because the defendant had nothing to do with him to prove that he is and to object completely to the accusation;
- 2) object to certain parts of the charge;
- 3) the Criminal Code, which provides for a more lenient punishment for the announced charge objecting to the correctness of the classification, arguing that the article should be amended to report;
- 4) the guilt of the defendant, citing mitigating circumstances justify a lower level of responsibility;
- 5) that the defendant does not incur criminal liability can prove. to cite defensive facts in these bars, this or that emphasizing the rules and not just talking about the fact that the evidence is questionable should. It is up to the lawyer to back up all of this with clear evidence must state the exact circumstances.

The lawyer's speech is only to receive the judge in the form in which it is complete and on time and the content of the speech is the truth about the opinions of the judges they will achieve their goal only if they are convinced that they are. The defense attorney's speech should be clear. Uncertain, superficial, work-related unsettled opinions make speech difficult, interest in the service of judges does not arouse, is not useful for the formation of real confidence in judges, at which point it loses its credibility. The exact circumstances of the case in the speech are clear talk about evidence work, draw clear conclusions, and so on. Helping the court make the next verdict is the culmination of a defense speechThe goal is this. By the time the defender enters his speech, he is himself should be fully open to the final conclusion while striving and presenting it to the court. The defense attorney's point of view is the court's you have to strive hard. Consequently, he sued only the principled, legal case reasonable, proposal to decide on the case materials possible. The content of the speech is the court, and along with the court, the defense is also a court inquiry should be marked by the work we have learned. It is subject to judicial inquiry the defense attorney should carefully monitor the questions asked to the interrogated, which are supervised by judges. Personal data of the defense judge, words should not be overlooked. It's about the judges about the case know what their thoughts will be and logically justify their opinions with which they must either process their ideas or reject them. This is where the defense's responsibilities come from: what the judges think to understand this idea without knowing that they are. When you understand,

the management does not hear, strengthen or modify ours with evidence. The defender himself has to convince the person who isn't saying anything. The defending judge is nothing more than that knows that he is waiting for an objection to a suspicion; not so clear, not so big knows that he is waiting for confirmation of an unformed thought. But the judge is clear on that does not know what to expect.

The right to qualified legal assistance is guaranteed at any stage of the investigation and court proceedings. Advocacy provides legal assistance to citizens, businesses and organizations. The organization and procedure of the Bar shall be determined by law. "

The protection of the constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens by a lawyer in criminal cases in the courts is recognized as protection.

When a lawyer acts as a defense counsel in criminal proceedings, he or she shall be entitled to a fair, but equitable, sentence to the defendant, regardless of the social danger, gravity, seriousness, or anti-state nature of the crime committed by his or her client. forced to strive for a relatively lenient sentence. This is because the procedural duty of a lawyer requires that attention be paid only to mitigating circumstances, his human qualities, his positive role and behavior in society, as well as the negative and unlawful actions of the victim.

Because this duty is sometimes based not on the facts of the case, but on the inner feelings of the victim, outraged by the horrific details of the crime, affected by the plight of the victim, under pressure from the public or the media, or by other political forces. under the influence of which the courts prevent unjust judgments and decisions.

The defense speech of the lawyer during the trial is of particular importance. Because a well-thought-out defense speech can have a big impact on the outcome of a lawsuit. "Adokat's defense speech is the culmination of his speeches in the criminal case," said the famous scientist MS Strogovich. It is in the defense speech that the lawyer presents his conclusions on the case, his objections to the whole charge or part of it to the court, and interprets the case from the point of view of defense. All this requires great skill from the defender. This is the result of hard work to protect the rights and legitimate interests of the protected person, without compromising the possibility of harming the defendant and ignoring the circumstances that may serve his benefit.

Of course, the style of the defense depends on the content of the case and the knowledge and experience of the lawyer. Sometimes defensive speech is expressed in a warm, uplifting, bright and beautiful way.

Sometimes it is characterized by a step-by-step analysis of factual situations, such as step-by-step calculations with exact numbers, comparison of dates, and so on. In some cases, it is preferable to argue with the prosecutor in the defense, if the element of debate is evident, and in some cases to frustratingly describe all the details that could be used to protect the defendant identified in the trial. All of this is acceptable, and it is not possible to set mandatory rules for everyone on this issue.

One of the peculiarities of the defense is that the defense attorney does not deny the factual nature and legal qualifications of the defendant, but describes the mitigating circumstances of the defendant. Such a situation arises in the following cases: 1. The crime has taken place and the defendant's actions have a criminal element; 2. Confession of the defendant that he participated in the committed criminal act or committed it personally; 3. The information obtained during the judicial investigation shall indicate that the guilt of the defendant has been proved; 4. The actions of the defendant are properly qualified by the articles of the Criminal Code. In such cases, a defense speech is drawn up by finding the defendant's guilt and mitigating circumstances. This requires great skill from the lawyer.

In practice, it is known that in this case, some lawyers prepare the same pattern of defense, which can be used in almost all cases. For example, they compose a defense speech limited to superficially stating that the defendant has no previous convictions, is young, has a foster parent, and has a positive description of work and study. However, for this method to be effective, all the circumstances of the case: the defendant's marital status, upbringing, attitude to the crime, the victim, his place in society, the circumstances that led to the crime must be expressed in speech.

Even after a well-thought-out defense speech, it is possible to adapt it to the situation, depending on the changes in some circumstances in the court proceedings. However, it should be borne in mind that even if the prosecutor denies the accusation, the defense counsel must not only agree with him, but also make a reasoned speech with a thorough analysis of the circumstances of the case. Because the prosecutor's refusal to plead guilty does not yet mean that the court will acquit him. Therefore, in such a case, it is necessary to support the opinion of the prosecutor in the defense, as well as to draw attention to the shortcomings in the case file, violations of procedural norms, and so on.

Some attorneys engage in nonsense, in other words, in the defense of a defense, by making a statement that is irrelevant to the case, or by

dwelling in detail on less important matters in the case file. This reduces the impact of the defense and sometimes leads to legitimate objections from the court.

Sometimes, no matter how well-structured the defense system and speech are, how well-defended the defense is, and how shallow the evidence in the case file is, the defendant may be convicted unjustifiably and unfairly. In such cases, the lawyer should not be discouraged. Because, firstly, in the process of composing a good speech, the lawyer's professional skills increase, secondly, the defense attorney demonstrates conscientious performance of his duties before the defendant and his relatives, and thirdly, the opportunity to reconsider the case in the courts of the next instance.

The speech should be not only well-structured, but also presented in a beautiful and fluent voice. The tone of the lawyer, the gestures and actions during the speech should be carefully thought out in advance. It is advisable to repeat and study several times before the speech in different forms. To do this, the lawyer can first practice in front of a mirror or any relative or friend.

When delivering a speech, the lawyer should look at the audience's face as much as possible. One of the biggest mistakes is to read a defense speech in the same tone, staring at one point. If the case contains facts, dates and figures that are not very memorable, they should be recorded on a separate sheet. As much as possible, the speech should be narrated in a slow, fluent, passionate, and at the same time calm voice.

The lawyer also observed a short pause during the speech in order to draw the audience's attention to some important aspects of the case or to draw attention to himself in a peaceful, orderly atmosphere in the courtroom, and then resumed his speech in the previous spirit. It is advisable to continue.

REFERENCE:

1. Sobir usmonov (2007) "Yuristning nutq madaniyati" ó'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashriyoti-Toshkent
2. S.Raxmonova.(2015) "Sud muhokamasining umumiy shartlari" Toshkent
3. www.ziyonet.uz
4. <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url>

5. <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://www.wordsmyth.net>
6. <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://www.macmillandictionary.com/dictionary/british/attorney&ved>